

Research

Study on improving Fenton oxidation process by coagulation

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Abstract: *In this study, Fenton oxidation process was improved by coupling of coagulation and further Fenton oxidation. A series of experiments such as coagulation, Fenton oxidation alone and the coupled coagulation–Fenton process were conducted with wastewater sample from pesticide industry. Compared with the Fenton process alone, the coupled coagulation–Fenton process has a good effect. In the coagulation step, 300 mg L⁻¹ polyaluminium chloride (PAC) and 200 mg L⁻¹ polyferric sulphate (PFS) were flocculated. In coupled process, the method of using 500 mg L⁻¹ H₂O₂, 400 mg L⁻¹ FeSO₄·7H₂O, pH 3 and 30 min. reaction time was adopted. The COD removal rate can be raised from 53.65% to 97%, the sludge sediment was reduced by 25%, and the cost of wastewater treatment was reduced by 33.85% by this process. The coupled coagulation–Fenton oxidation process has obvious economic and environmental benefits.*

Keywords: *Fenton oxidation process; Improving; Coagulation; Chemical oxygen demand*

1. Introduction

The waste generated from the industries creates serious effect on living thing existing on the earth. Some waste that much toxic in nature that it will damage for long life. In those categories pesticide industries play an important role (Cooke et al. 2004). Several hundred pesticides of different chemical nature are currently used for agricultural purposes all over the world. Because of their widespread use, they are detected in various environmental matrices, such as soil, water and air (Milena et al. 2006). Pesticide manufacture generates wastewater containing toxic, chemically stable, and recalcitrant compounds (Zapata et al. 2009). Pesticide wastewater

distinguishes itself because of its toxic and persistent nature in the environment. This wastewater depicts wide variation in its characteristics based on the pesticide production; raw materials used and water consumption and wastewater flow (Babu and Venkatesan 2011).

Advanced oxidation process (AOP) has been successfully used to treat industrial wastewaters that are non-biodegradable and toxic to microorganisms (Dutta et al. 2001). Among Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOPs), the Fenton process can be used as a chemical alternative to treat non-biodegradable wastewater. Fenton system consists of ferrous salts combined with hydrogen peroxide, whereas Fenton-like system uses iron powder (Fe^0) in reaction with H_2O_2 , at optimum pH, to produce $\bullet\text{OH}$ for the destruction of the organic pollutants (Abdullah et al. 2014). A large number of studies have shown that the high COD value of wastewater can be successfully treated by combining physical and chemical processes. The combination of coagulation and Fenton oxidation has been successfully used for the treatment of highly contaminated wastewater such as cosmetics, olive-mill, textile, and pharmaceutical effluents (Ginos et al. 2006), (Xing and Sun 2009), (Perdigón-Melón et al. 2010), (Gema Pliego et al. 2012).

In this study, Fenton process was improved by coupling of preliminary coagulation step and further Fenton oxidation. The aim of this study was to enhance the removal of chemical oxygen demand (COD) in wastewater from pesticide industry and to minimize the sludge production after Fenton process. Polyaluminium chloride (PAC) and polyferric sulfate (PFS) were used as coagulants without adjustment of pH and the optimal coagulation conditions (coagulant dose and coagulation precipitation time) were determined. Fenton oxidation process alone was carried out with the raw wastewater sample and the optimal Fenton oxidation conditions (initial pH value, dosage of H_2O_2 and FeSO_4 , and reaction time) were determined. In the coupled process, $500 \text{ mg L}^{-1} \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$, $400 \text{ mg L}^{-1} \text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, pH 3 and 30 min reaction time were used. COD removal rate can be increased from 53.65% to 97%, sludge content was reduced by 25%, and the cost of wastewater treatment was reduced by 33.85%. Coagulation Fenton coupling oxidation process has obvious economic and environmental benefits.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Raw wastewater

In this experiment, the wastewater sample was collected from the second sedimentation tank of Hubei Nongchang Pesticides Chemicals Company Limited wastewater pond. The main physicochemical characteristics of wastewater sample are given in Table 1.

Table 1 Physiochemical characteristics of pesticide industry wastewater sample

Sr. No.	Parameters	Range
1.	COD (Chemical Oxygen Demand)	1100 mg/L
2.	pH	6 - 9
3.	SS (Suspended Solid)	220 mg/L
4.	Turbidity	18~25 NTU
5.	Ammonia/Nitrogen	830 mg/L
6.	TP (Total Phosphorus)	15 mg/L
7.	Colour	yellowish brown
8.	Odour	Objectionable

2.2 Main reagents

The main reagents used in this experiment were polyaluminium chloride (PAC) and polyferric sulfate (PFS) with a mass concentration of 2%, 30% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), ferrous sulfate heptahydrate (FeSO₄.7H₂O), concentrated sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) and sodium hydroxide (NaOH). All chemicals used for the experiments were at least analytical grade.

2.3 Main equipment

The COD was measured using a colorimetric method after digestion of the sample. HACH-DR 200 digestion instrument and HACH-DR 3900 spectrometer (Shanghai Shangguo Instrument Technology Co., Ltd.) were used for COD measurements. Turbidity was measured by using a WGZ-IB type turbidimeter (Shanghai Xinrui Instrument Co., Ltd.). PHS-3G pH meter (Youlebo

Technology Co., Ltd.), YP1002 electronic analytical balance (Shanghai Chuyan Laboratory Equipment Co., Ltd.), HJ-6A six-batch agitator (Changzhou future instrument manufacturing co. LTD), 1000 ml volumetric flask, beakers, pipettes and dropper were used.

2.4 Experimental methods and procedures

2.4.1 Coagulation process

After measuring the initial value of wastewater sample, 1L beakers were taken and 500 mL of wastewater sample was taken and put it into the beaker. In this experiment, 2% polyaluminium chloride (PAC) and 2% polyferric sulfate (PFS) were used to achieve the best coagulation effect by changing the amount of the two without pH adjustment. After the required amount of coagulant solutions were added into the beakers, the beakers were placed on the six-batch agitator. First, the initial speed was set as 150 rpm/min, and the beakers were quickly stirred for 5min, then the speed was adjusted as 60 rpm/min. Then, the wastewater was stationary for 30 minutes to react and settle out the flocs. After standing for 30min, the supernatant of wastewater was taken for the determination of COD and SS in the wastewater sample. COD and SS removal rate were measured.

2.4.2 Fenton process

After measuring the initial value of wastewater sample, 1L beakers were taken and 500 mL of wastewater sample was filled into them. The pH value was adjusted to the desired value with concentrated sulfuric acid. The appropriate amount of 30% hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) and ferrous sulfate heptahydrate ($FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$) were added and the mixture was stirred at 200 rpm for 1 minute. After that the mixture was allowed to stand with a certain period of reaction time. After a period of time, the pH of wastewater was adjusted to 8~9 with sodium hydroxide solution. The supernatant was taken for the determination of COD and COD removal rate was measured. Then, wet sludge was taken from the sludge level at the bottom of the beakers. Finally, the volume of sludge dehydrated by centrifugation at 4000 rpm for 5 min was determined.

2.4.3 The coupled treatment (coagulation followed by Fenton process)

In order to enhance the removal of chemical oxygen demand (COD) and to minimize the sludge production at the lowest treatment cost, the strategy of coupling coagulation with Fenton oxidation was adopted. Thus, 500 mL of the clarified wastewater treated by coagulation under optimal conditions previously selected was further subjected to the Fenton process. For the process

parameters, initial pH value previously found when applying the Fenton alone (pH=3) was selected. However, the dosage of $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and H_2O_2 were optimized again for 1 hour reaction time by varying their amount from 100 mg L^{-1} to 600 mg L^{-1} $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and from 100 mg L^{-1} to 600 mg L^{-1} H_2O_2 , respectively. In the coupled treatment, the optimal dosage of $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and H_2O_2 found when applying the Fenton alone were not used because part of the organic load was removed in the coagulation treatment step. The supernatant of wastewater was taken at different time periods in the reaction process to measure the COD value. Then, wet sludge was taken from the sludge level at the bottom of the beakers. Finally, the volume of sludge dehydrated by centrifugation at 4000 rpm for 5 min was determined.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Coagulation process

The wastewater from pesticide industry was subjected to a coagulation process. To obtain the optimal coagulation conditions, the effect of three variables, including polyaluminium chloride (PAC) dosage, coagulation precipitation time and combination of PAC and polyferric sulfate (PFS) dosage on the COD reduction and SS removal were evaluated.

3.1.1 Effect of polyaluminium chloride (PAC) dosage on removal of COD and SS

Figure 1 presents the study carried out to determine the optimal dosage of PAC in the range of 50 to 400 mg/L on the removal of COD and suspended solids (SS) without pH adjustment. Since the optimal pH range that PAC can adapt to is 7-10, and the pH of raw pesticide wastewater is 7.6, it is not necessary to adjust the pH of wastewater. As it can be seen from Figure 1, the SS removal increased continuously with PAC dosage until it reaches a value of 300 mg L^{-1} . When increasing the dosage more than 300 mg L^{-1} , the SS removal decreased obviously. The COD removal increased a little with an increase in the dosage of PAC, from 18.8% for the dosage of 50 mg L^{-1} PAC to 28% for the dosage of 300 mg L^{-1} PAC but later decreased slightly. This fact could be explained that excessive PAC dosage led to the reduction of flocculation efficiency because of the overdosing effect of the coagulant and charge reversal of negatively charged colloidal particles. The increasing dosage of PAC could also lead the destabilization of colloidal particles, resulting in the reduction of flocculation efficiency (Zhu et al. 2011). Thus, the reduction of flocculation efficiency was obtained at excess flocculants dosage. According to the results, it is determined that

the optimum PAC dosage was 300 mg L⁻¹, obtaining the COD removal of 28% and SS removal of 72.4%.

Fig.1 Effect of 2% PAC dosage on COD and SS removal by the coagulation process

3.1.2 Effect of coagulation precipitation time on removal of COD and SS

The experiments were carried out by varying coagulation precipitation time as 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70 and 80 minutes, respectively. The initial pH value of wastewater was 7.6 and the fixed amount of PAC dosage was 300 mg L⁻¹. The effect of coagulation precipitation time on the removal of COD and suspended solids is shown in Figure 2. According to Figure 2, it can be seen that the removal rate of COD and SS increased with the extension of coagulation precipitation time. When the precipitation time was 10 min, the removal rate of COD and SS were 23.2% and 58.6%. When the precipitation time was 30 min, the removal rate of COD and SS increased to 28.5% and 71.0%. Therefore, the extension of coagulation precipitation time on the removal of COD and suspended solids has certain enhancement. But when the precipitation time exceeded 30 min, the COD removal rate decreased slightly but the subsequent increased SS removal rate was

relatively slow. Thus, in this study, the optimal coagulation precipitation time was 30 minutes, the COD and SS removal rates were 28.5% and 71.0% respectively.

Fig.2 Effect of coagulation precipitation time on COD and SS removal by the coagulation process

3.1.3 Effect of the combination of PAC and PFS dosage on removal of COD and SS

The effect of the combination of PAC and PFS dosage on the removal of COD and suspended solids is shown in Figure 3. Numerous studies show that dosing organic flocculant or inorganic coagulant simultaneously had better flocculation performance than dosing organic flocculant or inorganic coagulant alone (T. Chen et al. 2010),(Wei et al. 2009). Therefore, optimal polyaluminium chloride (PAC) dosage of 300 mg L^{-1} obtained from earlier experiment was kept constant and the effect of polyferric sulfate (PFS) dosage on removal of COD and SS was investigated by varying from 50 mg L^{-1} to 400 mg L^{-1} . It can be seen from the Figure 3, when the dosage of PFS was within the range of $50\text{-}200 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, the removal rate of COD and SS increased from 28.2% to 40.3% and from 75.2% to 84.3%. It was clear that the addition of PFS coagulant increased further coagulation efficiency. This was mainly due to polyferric sulfate (PFS) can be

effective in the conventional coagulation process, because the use of PFS can reduce the complicated reactions caused by iron–salt hydrolysis, which provide simpler and more precise control on the coagulation reactions (Po and Fung Hwa 2002). In addition, PFS floc is generated by the ferric sulfate hydrolysis in water by polymerization, at intermediate gel precipitation in the process of transformation, which can absorb the colloid particles and suspended solids and coagulate each other (Zouboulis et al. 2008). However, when the dosage of PFS exceeded 200 mg L⁻¹, the removal rate of COD and SS significantly decreased to 29.6% and 70.2% respectively. The excessive PFS dose increased the (color number) CN of the wastewater (W. Chen et al. 2019). On the other hand, too much PFS also inhibited the colloids from condensing (Xing and Sun 2009; Moussas and Zouboulis 2009). Therefore, in this experiment, the best removal of SS (84.3%) and the optimal removal (40.3%) of COD can be obtained at 300 mg L⁻¹ PAC and 200 mg L⁻¹ PFS, respectively.

In summary, the removal of COD and SS obtained by coagulation treatment (pH 7.6, PAC dosage 300 mg L⁻¹ and PFS dosage 200 mg L⁻¹) are presented in Table 2.

Fig.3 Effect of 2% PAC (300 mg/L) + 2% PFS dosage on COD and SS removal by the coagulation process

Table 2 Removal efficiency of coagulation treatment

Parameters	C_o	C_{CF}	$R\%_{CF}$
COD (mg L^{-1})	1100	656.7	40.3
SS (mg L^{-1})	220	34.54	84.3

C_o , initial concentration; C_{CF} , concentration after the coagulation treatment; $R\%_{CF}$, removal efficiency in the coagulation treatment

3.2 Fenton process

To evaluate the efficiency of Fenton process, 500 mL of raw wastewater sample was treated by Fenton process alone. In order to achieve the best Fenton oxidation conditions, the factors affecting the efficiency of Fenton process on COD removal rate (initial pH value, dosage of H_2O_2 and $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and reaction time) were determined.

Table 3 Single factor experiment design

Influence Factors	Initial pH	Reaction time (min)	30% Hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) dosage (mg/L)	Ferrous sulfate heptahydrate ($\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) dosage (mg/L)
Initial pH	2	40	1000	800
	3	40	1000	800
	4	40	1000	800
	5	40	1000	800
	6	40	1000	800
	7	40	1000	800
Reaction time	3	10	1000	800
	3	20	1000	800
	3	30	1000	800
	3	40	1000	800
	3	50	1000	800

	3	60	1000	800
30% Hydrogen peroxide (H ₂ O ₂) dosage	3	40	400	800
	3	40	600	800
	3	40	800	800
	3	40	1000	800
	3	40	1200	800
	3	40	1400	800
Ferrous sulfate heptahydrate (FeSO ₄ .7H ₂ O) dosage	3	40	1000	400
	3	40	1000	600
	3	40	1000	800
	3	40	1000	1000
	3	40	1000	1200
	3	40	1000	1400

3.2.1 Effect of initial pH value on COD removal rate

According to the literature, it is well known that the pH plays an important role of hydroxyl radical generation in the Fenton reaction (Xiao et al. 2017) . The pH value of wastewater was adjusted to the desired value with concentrated sulfuric acid prior to Fenton reaction. Low pH favours Fenton oxidation (Deng and Englehardt 2006) , so according to the design experiments 1-6 in the Table 3, the experiments were carried out a pH range from 2 to 7. Figure 4 shows the effect of initial pH value on COD removal of wastewater treated with a fixed amount of 1000 mg L⁻¹ H₂O₂, 800 mg L⁻¹ FeSO₄.7H₂O and reaction time was 40 minutes. As shown in Figure 4, the COD removal rate increased from 32.53% to 48.68% with the increase of pH value and then the COD removal rate started to decrease at pH more than 3. The optimal COD removal was reached at pH 3 with 48.68% COD removal rate. It is because the too high or too low pH was not conducive to removing COD. COD removal rate under acidic conditions was generally higher than that under

neutral conditions. When the pH value was too low, it was not beneficial to generate hydroxyl radicals due to their stability of H_2O_2 . While the pH value was too high, it was easy to make Fe^{2+} precipitate resulting in the loss of catalytic oxidation ability and the reduction of hydroxyl radical formation (Martín-Pascual et al. 2016). Moreover, the formation of the ferric hydroxide complexes also led to a reduction of hydroxyl radicals at high pH value (Kutukcuoglu 2015). Therefore, pH 3 was chosen as the optimal pH for the Fenton process in this study.

Fig. 4 Effect of initial pH value on COD removal in the Fenton process

3.2.2 Effect of reaction time on COD removal rate

In this section, according to the design experiments 7-12 in the Table 3, the experiments were conducted with different reaction time ranging from 10 minutes to 60 minutes. The pH was controlled at 3 and the dosage of $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and H_2O_2 were fixed at 1000 mg L^{-1} and 800 mg L^{-1} , respectively. Figure 5 shows the removal of COD at different reaction time. As shown in Figure 5, the COD removal rate was very fast within 40 minutes of reaction time. In the stage of reaction time from 10 min to 40 min, COD removal rate increased rapidly from 22.33% to 53.65%. After 40 minutes, COD removal rate was still increasing, reaching 54.67% when the reaction time was 60 minutes. However, compared with the speed of removal rate in the range of 10-40 minutes,

the speed of removal rate was relatively slow with little change basically. This was due to the consumption of H_2O_2 was completed when the reaction time was more than 40 minutes. On the other hand, it demonstrated that with the extension of reaction time, Fe^{2+} and H_2O_2 can fully react to generate the hydroxyl radical. Meanwhile, the contact time of organic contaminant and Fenton reagent also increase and extended, resulting in the effective degradation of organic matter. The macromolecular organic compounds were degraded into the micro-molecular organic compositions by the hydroxyl radical at the beginning, and the COD removal rate was low due to the change of the molecular weight with a little degradation reaction. However, with the increase of reaction time, the micro-molecular organic compositions were degraded into carbon dioxide and water, resulting in the reduction of COD (Xiao et al. 2017). Hence, at the long reaction time range, the selection of actual reaction time was needed for the Fenton process. In this study, the optimal reaction time was chosen as 40 minutes.

Fig.5 Effect of reaction time on COD removal in the Fenton process

3.2.3 Effect of H₂O₂ dosage on COD removal rate

In this part, according to the design experiments 13-18 in the Table 3, the experiments were carried out with a range of H₂O₂ dosage from 400 mg L⁻¹ to 1400 mg L⁻¹. Figure 6 shows the removal of COD at different H₂O₂ dosage. The initial pH value was controlled at 3, and the fixed amount of FeSO₄·7H₂O dosage and reaction time were 800 mg L⁻¹ and 40 minutes. When the dosage of H₂O₂ increased from 400 mg L⁻¹ to 1000 mg L⁻¹, the COD removal increased sharply from 29.32% to 55.45%. However, the dosage of H₂O₂ varied from 1000 mg L⁻¹ to 1400 mg L⁻¹, the COD removal rate decreased slightly from 55.45% to 45.22%. This indicated that the appropriate amount of H₂O₂ dosage enhanced the COD removal rate in the Fenton process. The decrease of COD removal rate was attributed to the competitive reaction between hydroxyl radicals and H₂O₂ to generate hydroperoxyl radicals with excess dosage of H₂O₂ (Jorfi et al. 2016). The hydroperoxyl radical was also an effective oxidant itself, but the hydroperoxyl radicals were much less reactive and did not contribute to the oxidative degradation of organic substrates, which occurred only by reaction with hydroxyl radical (Kutukcuoglu 2015),(Rodrigues et al. 2013). Thus, the optimal H₂O₂ dosage was 1000 mg L⁻¹ with 55.45 % COD removal rate.

Fig.6 Effect of H₂O₂ dosage on COD removal in the Fenton process

3.2.4 Effect of FeSO₄·7H₂O dosage on COD removal rate

According to the design experiments 19-24 in the Table 3, the experiments were carried out with a range of FeSO₄·7H₂O dosage from 400 mg L⁻¹ to 1400 mg L⁻¹. In this study, the initial pH value, H₂O₂ dosage and reaction time of Fenton process conditions were 3, 1000 mg L⁻¹ and 40 minutes, respectively. Figure 7 shows the removal of COD at different FeSO₄·7H₂O dosage. As it can be seen from Figure 7, when the dosage of FeSO₄·7H₂O was within the range of 400 mg L⁻¹ to 800 mg L⁻¹, the COD removal rate was better and the COD removal rate increased from 26.43% to 50.55%. When the dosage of FeSO₄·7H₂O was more than 800 mg L⁻¹, the COD removal rate decreased to 41.24%. At the same time, it can be clearly seen in the experiment that the color of iron mud changed green with the increasing dosage of FeSO₄·7H₂O. This was due to the increasing amount of ferric hydroxo complexes and HO• generated by the redox reaction with the increasing dosage of FeSO₄·7H₂O (Ma and Xia 2009). When the Fe²⁺ dosage was in excess, a large amount of hydroxyl radicals was generated in a short time leading to the consumption of hydroxyl radicals by side reactions. Further, the effective utilization rate of hydroxyl radicals reduced causing by side reactions (Esteves et al. 2016). The use of a much higher Fe²⁺ concentration could result in the self-scavenging of hydroxyl radicals by Fe²⁺, leading to a decrease in the treatment performance (Y. Wang et al. 2011). Therefore, the optimal COD removal rate was 50.55% obtained at 800 mg L⁻¹ FeSO₄·7H₂O.

In summary, the Fenton process alone allows a significant reduction of the organic matter present in the raw wastewater. When the addition amount of FeSO₄·7H₂O is 800 mg L⁻¹, the addition amount of 30% H₂O₂ is 1000 mg L⁻¹, the initial pH is 3, and the reaction time is 40 min, the reaction is the best condition. The removal efficiency obtained by Fenton process alone is presented in Table 4.

Table 4 Removal efficiency of Fenton process alone

Parameter	C _O	C _F	R% _F
COD (mg L ⁻¹)	1100	509.85	53.65

C_O, initial concentration; C_F, final concentration after Fenton process; R%_F, removal efficiency by Fenton treatment

Fig.7 Effect of FeSO₄·7H₂O dosage on COD removal in the Fenton process

3.3 The coupled treatment (coagulation followed by Fenton process)

In this experiment, 500 mL of the clarified wastewater treated by coagulation under optimal conditions previously selected was further subjected to the Fenton process. Initial pH value was fixed at their optimum conditions obtained when applying the Fenton alone. However, the dosage of FeSO₄·7H₂O and H₂O₂ were optimized again for 1hour reaction time by varying their amount from 100 mg L⁻¹ to 600 mg L⁻¹ FeSO₄·7H₂O and from 100 mg L⁻¹ to 600mg L⁻¹ H₂O₂, respectively. The supernatant of wastewater was taken at different time periods in the reaction process to measure the COD value. Figure 8 shows the COD removal rate during combined treatment at different dosage of H₂O₂ when FeSO₄·7H₂O dosage was fixed at 400 mg L⁻¹ for 1hour reaction time. The COD removal rate increased with the increase of H₂O₂ dosage and reached the maximum COD removal rate (97.01%) at 500 mg L⁻¹ H₂O₂.

Fig.8 Effect of H₂O₂ dosage on COD removal in the coupled process (coagulation followed by Fenton process)

Figure 9 shows the COD removal rate during combined treatment at different dosage of FeSO₄.7H₂O when H₂O₂ dosage was fixed at 500 mg L⁻¹ for 1hour reaction time. As shown in Figure 9, the increasing dosage of FeSO₄.7H₂O to 400 mg L⁻¹ increased the removal of COD to 97.35 %. When the dosage of FeSO₄.7H₂O was more than 400 mg L⁻¹, the removal of COD decreased with the increase of FeSO₄.7H₂O dosage. According to the results shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9, the COD removal rate occurs very rapidly in the first 10-30 min of reaction time for all H₂O₂ dosage and FeSO₄.7H₂O dosage tested. When the reaction time was more than 30 min, the COD removal rate began to flatten. Therefore, reaction time of 30 min was adopted in the combined process tests.

As above-mentioned, at the end of Fenton oxidation stage of the coupled treatment, the best COD removal (97 %) was obtained using 300 mg L⁻¹ PAC and 200 mg L⁻¹ PFS in coagulation stage, 500 mg L⁻¹ H₂O₂, 400 mg L⁻¹ FeSO₄.7H₂O, pH 3 and 30 min reaction time in the Fenton oxidation stage. The COD removal efficiency obtained by combining coagulation and Fenton treatments are presented in Table 5.

Table 5 Removal efficiency of the coupled treatment (coagulation followed by Fenton process)

Parameter	C_0	$R\%_{CF}$	C_{CF}	$R\%_F$	C_F
COD(mg L^{-1})	1100	40.3	656.7	97	19.71

C_0 , initial concentration; $R\%_{CF}$, removal efficiency in the coagulation treatment; C_{CF} , concentration after the coagulation treatment; $R\%_F$, removal efficiency by Fenton treatment; C_F , final concentration after combined coagulation and Fenton treatments

Fig. 9 Effect of $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ dosage on COD removal in the coupled process (coagulation followed by Fenton process)

3.4 Comparison of the Fenton process alone and the coupled treatment (coagulation followed by Fenton process)

In order to investigate the effectiveness of the coupled treatment (coagulation followed by Fenton process) performed, the removal of COD, the cost performance and final generation of iron-containing sludge of the coupled treatment were compared with those of the Fenton process alone and the results are shown in the following Table 6. It can be seen from the Table that, the removal of COD obtained by the Fenton process alone was 53.65%. Meanwhile, using Fenton

after (PAC + PFS) coagulation improved the COD removal efficiency by 43.35%, and which can reach 97 %. While the treatment cost for one cubic meter of wastewater treated by the coupled treatment was 0.43 \$, the treatment cost treated by Fenton process alone was 0.65 \$. Coagulation followed by Fenton reduced the treatment cost by 33.85%. This is due to the main cost of Fenton process was the cost of H₂O₂. This fact could be explained that when compared to Fenton process alone, the consumption of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) dosage is reduced one time in the coupled treatment. Considering the final sludge sediment, while the volume of the final sludge sediment generated in the coupled treatment was 225 L, the volume of the final sludge sediment generated in Fenton process alone was 300 L. The reason is that the yield of Fenton sludge is dependent upon the ratio and volume of the added reagents (Bautista et al. 2008). From the previously selected experiments, it can be known that the optimal amount of the Fenton reagents added to the combined treatment were 500 mg L⁻¹ H₂O₂ and 400 mg L⁻¹ FeSO₄.7H₂O and the optimal amount of the Fenton reagents added to the Fenton process alone were 1000 mg L⁻¹ H₂O₂ and 800 mg L⁻¹ FeSO₄.7H₂O respectively. Therefore, the coupled treatment (coagulation followed by Fenton process) also reduced the final sludge sediment by 25%. In the coupled treatment, coagulation reduces the initial organic concentration and consequently the oxidant requirements for the Fenton process, optimizing the overall treatment cost. Additionally, a decrease of the initial organic content could enhance the efficiency of the Fenton process, obtaining a final effluent with higher biodegradability (G. Pliego et al. 2014). Hence, coagulation before Fenton was beneficial to improve the Fenton process. Moreover, the above-mentioned results indicate a positive potential solution for using coagulation and Fenton treatments in sequence to treat industrial wastewater from pesticide manufacturing.

Table 6 Comparison of the Fenton process alone and the coupled treatment

Treatments	Treatment cost (\$/m ³)	COD removal rate (%)	Final sludge volume (L)
Fenton Process alone	0.65	53.65	300
Coupled Treatment (coagulation followed by Fenton process)	0.43	97	225

3.5 Action mechanism analysis of Fenton method after coagulation

The efficiency of the Fenton process depends on the properties of wastewater, the pH value, the dosage of hydrogen peroxide, ferrous ion concentration and the reaction time. Fenton's chemistry uses hydrogen peroxides (H_2O_2) and iron salts where the effectiveness of H_2O_2 is improved by iron through generation of highly reactive hydroxyl radicals. The iron acts as a catalyst in the process. If the hydroxyl radical is the key intermediate, the initiation step would be (Gogate et al. 2002).

Afterwards, OH^\bullet radicals may either oxidize another Fe^{2+} to Fe^{3+} (termination step):

Or they may give reaction with H_2O_2 (propagation step):

Also, the OH^\bullet radical may oxidize other species (substrate) present in solution:

Ferrous ion reacts with hydrogen peroxide at acidic pH in ambient conditions, producing ferric ion and hydroxyl radical OH^\bullet mentioned above (reaction 1). According to the above reaction 2 and reaction 3, both H_2O_2 and Fe^{+2} can react with OH^\bullet and therefore both can inhibit the oxidation reactions if either of them is not in the optimal dosage (Tang and Huang 1996). Many authors suggested Fe^{+2} to H_2O_2 mass ratio to be optimal at 1 to 10, but it must be optimized for particular wastewater to minimize scavenging effects (Torrades et al. 2003). Therefore, in this work, after several experiments, it was found that when the amount of hydrogen peroxide added was 500 mg L^{-1} and the amount of ferrous sulfate added was 400 mg L^{-1} , the removal rate reached the highest. When the amount of hydrogen peroxide added was more than 500 mg L^{-1} and the amount of ferrous sulfate added was more than 400 mg L^{-1} , the removal rate decreased rapidly. According to the above reaction 2 and reaction 3, this can be explained by the scavenging effect of the excessive amounts of H_2O_2 and Fe^{+2} on OH^\bullet . Fe^{3+} produced can react with H_2O_2 and hydroperoxyl radical in the so-called Fenton-like reaction, which leads to regenerating Fe^{+2} (reactions 4) (Vandevivere et al. 1998). Hydroxyl radicals may react with organics starting a chain

reaction (reactions 5) (Bianco et al. 2011). This hydroxyl radical attacks organic molecules by abstracting a hydrogen atom or by adding to the double bonds. Organic molecules are then totally mineralized to carbon dioxide and water (Huston and Pignatello 1999).

The oxidizing potential of the hydroxyl radical is pH dependent, and varies from $E^0 = 1.8$ V at neutral pH to +2.7 V in acidic solutions (El-Morsi et al. 2002). The ferrous ion can catalyze hydrogen peroxide for the production of OH^\bullet and the degradation of organic matter only under acidic conditions. However, when the solution is too acidic, H^+ concentration is high, which is not conducive to the reaction. When the solution is alkaline, Fe^{3+} ions begin to form flocs ($\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$) or goethite FeOOH and precipitate and H_2O_2 is also unstable and decomposes to give O_2 and H_2O and consequently loses its oxidizing properties (S. Wang 2008). Experiments showed that the removal rate of organic matter was higher under acidic conditions. Therefore, pH 3 was selected as the initial pH value. The acidic pH level around 3 is usually optimum for Fenton oxidation (Neyens and Baeyens 2003; Gogate and Pandit 2004). Experiments also demonstrated that the removal rate of COD increased with reaction time, but the first the removal rate was fast and then slow. 30 min was a better reaction time for this experiment.

4. Conclusions

In this work, the Fenton oxidation process was improved by coupling of coagulation and further Fenton oxidation to treat industrial wastewater from pesticide manufacturing and it was proved to be an efficient and promising method. The coagulation was carried out using polyaluminium chloride (PAC) and polyferric sulphate (PFS). Coagulation using 300 mg L^{-1} PAC and 200 mg L^{-1} PFS at pH 7.6 led to moderate removal of COD 40.3% and high removal of SS 84.3% reduction. Afterward, Fenton oxidation alone was conducted with raw wastewater and the removal of COD could be reduced 53.65% using 1000 mg L^{-1} H_2O_2 , 800 mg L^{-1} $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 40 min reaction time and pH 3. In the coupled treatment (coagulation followed by Fenton process), Fenton oxidation was carried out with wastewater pretreated by coagulation under optimal conditions previously selected. The selected optimal reaction conditions were 500 mg L^{-1} H_2O_2 , 400 mg L^{-1} $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 30 min reaction time and pH 3. Compared with Fenton oxidation alone, coagulation followed by Fenton process enhanced the removal of COD by 43.35%, and which can reach 97 % at the optimal reaction conditions. Fenton reaction time could be shortened to 30 min in the coupled treatment. Before Fenton oxidation, coagulation pretreatment was helpful to reduce

the needs of H₂O₂ dosage, to reduce the consumption of FeSO₄·7H₂O dosage and to reduce the initial organic concentration for the Fenton process. Furthermore, the remaining iron in wastewater after coagulation process also provides a suitable iron source for the Fenton oxidation process. At the same time, the generation of sludge sediment after Fenton oxidation was reduced by 25% and the cost of treating wastewater was reduced by 33.85% by this process. The treatment cost was relatively low and enhancement of COD removal rate with less sludge volume production, demonstrating the need to use them in combination. Therefore, a coupled coagulation–Fenton process was a cost effective, an efficient and promising wastewater treatment method for industrial wastewater from pesticide manufacturing.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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